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STUDENTS' PRODUCTIVITY AND TEACHERS' PEDAGOGY: BASIS FOR DEVELOPING A PEDAGOGICAL GUIDE FOR TLE INSTRUCTION

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This study examines the influence of teachers' teaching pedagogy on students' productivity in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) at Pinamukan Integrated School, with an emphasis on the efficacy of diverse instructional pedagogies and the obstacles faced by teachers. The research was reinforced by the Department of Education's (DepEd) directive to enhance student performance and engagement, as articulated in DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2015. This order encourages schools to implement strategies that foster a conducive learning environment and promote student accountability. Through stratified purposive sampling, 66 junior high school students were selected. The total population of TLE teachers was selected to provide insights into how they adapt their pedagogical approaches, which in turn affect students' productivity and contribute to their academic success.

Findings revealed the strong positive correlation between students' productivity and teachers' teaching pedagogy. However, teachers face considerable challenges, including difficulty in integrating technology into teaching, difficulty in engaging students during practical lessons, and the lack of student motivation or interest. To address these challenges, the study proposes a Pedagogical Guide for TLE Instruction, designed to enhance teachers' performance and increase students' productivity.

Keywords: Teaching Pedagogy, Students' Productivity

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